

GENDER SITUATION ANALYSIS AND NEEDS ASSESSMENT

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture

Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

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Overview

The current Deliverable 2.3: “Gender Analysis and Needs Assessment”, provides an overview of the gender dimension within the project by clearly articulating its relevance to all WPs. Moreover, is estimating how research findings apply to the specific needs of all sexes, and is considering all intersecting factors. The goal is to enhance the gender-sensitive dimension relevance in respect to the project team, results and activities.

The document is structured in 9 chapters. Chapter 1 is the introduction of gender equality and gender mainstreaming within the project. Chapter 2 provides the main Gender definitions and concepts, whilst Chapter 3 presents the project’s gender considerations and its Gender Equality Policy. The Gender Equality Framework is presented in Chapter 4, followed by the ENVISION Gender Situation Analysis and Needs Assessment in Chapter 5. The stakeholders’ gender responsiveness is presented next and the Gender Specific Project Dissemination is presented in Chapter 7. Chapter 8 analyses the Gender-Sensitive monitoring plan of the project and the deliverable closes up with the Conclusions Chapter.

1 Introduction

ENVISION contributes to the achievement of CAP's environmental objectives, offering the tools for the continuous, large scale and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability. These tools reinforce the monitoring of environmental- and climate-friendly agricultural practices stemming from EU policy ensuring that the agricultural production activities do not severely impact the climate and nature.

ENVISION fully exploits the wealth of data made available through GEOSS and Copernicus and its synergetic use with other data to develop data products. It makes use of heterogeneous types of available data (EO-based, in situ, open data, and historical on-field check data) and state-of-the-art technologies and methodologies (automatic pixel/texture/object-oriented change detection and classification methods, machine learning, data fusion, multi-source and multi-temporal data management) for providing a fully-automated and scalable toolbox of services, built in close interaction with its future customers.

Considering the implementation of a multi-stakeholder project it is vital to address gender equality to effectively achieve sustainable outcomes. Examining gender issues mitigates impediments to social and economic prosperity; reduces the possibility for gender bias; and improves the return on investment.

Gender equality is of utmost importance in the EU and it is explicitly included in the common values on which the Union is founded. The dimension of equality was initially examined as the principle of equal pay, but gender equality has over the years a series of Directives have been adopted in the Charter of Fundamental Rights in the EU which prohibits discrimination in all areas, recognizes the right to gender equality and promotes positive action for its promotion. Additionally, European Research Area (ERA) priority 4 focuses on gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research and innovation, by fully utilising gender diversity and equality.¹

The Consortium is set on a balanced gender mix whilst a number of managers in the Executive Board are female. The ratio between male – female team members is estimated to 58%-42% respectively and women occupy equally responsible position as all partners are committed to a Gender Equality Policy.

When it comes to stakeholders, gender equity is also a major issue. Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies (PAs and CBs) are in most cases staffed by both sexes but whether females occupy managerial positions is under investigation. The dimension of equal opportunities will be promoted by the project, whilst the needs of women employees in the field and the problems they encounter will be investigated aiming at the implementation of gender mainstreaming policies through the project.

Agricultural population has a significant gender dimension as farming is still regarded as a “man’s world. Women make crucial contributions in agriculture in all the developing country regions. Despite the fact that their roles vary across regions, women face gender-specific constraints that reduce their productivity and limit their contributions to agricultural production.

¹ Minimum Standards for Mainstreaming Gender Equality, The Gender Practitioners Collaborative.

The spread of technology is having a colossal impact on the labour market and the types of skills needed in the economy and society. However, gender mainstreaming is not well developed in digital single market policies and substantial discrepancies persist between different EU Member States. According to the “Women in Digital (WiD) Scoreboard” – the mechanisms put in place by the Commission to assess women’s inclusion in digital jobs, careers and entrepreneurship – stereotypes and preconceptions continue to create obstacles for women and girls. Even in those Member States where gender mainstreaming is more advanced it is confirmed that gender inequalities continue to prevent women from reaching their full potential and hinder EU societies from taking full advantage of women’s digital potential and current contributions.²

As it is obvious from the above gender issues play an important role in the areas of ENVISION’s focus and inequalities are seen. Therefore, gender is of high significance in the project’s research agenda. ENVISION will therefore go beyond merely processing statistics that present the gender balance of the consortium, into the inequalities faced by the agricultural and IT sector and measures that will ensure gender mainstreaming with the project’s results.

² European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) Gender Equality Index 2020 — Digitalisation and the future of work

2 Definitions and Concepts

Sex refers to the biologically determined characteristics of men and women in terms of reproductive organs and functions based on chromosomal complement and physiology. As such, sex is globally understood as the classification of living things as male or female.³

Gender refers to the social construction of women and men, of femininity and masculinity, which varies in time and place, and between cultures. The notion of gender appeared in the seventies and was put forward by feminist theorists who challenged the secondary position of women in society. It departs from the notion of sex to signal that biology or anatomy is not a destiny. It is important to distinguish clearly between gender and sex. These terms are often used interchangeably while they are conceptually distinctive.²

Gender equality refers to the situation where individuals of both sexes are free to develop their personal abilities and make choices without the limitations imposed by strict gender roles. The different behaviours, aspirations and needs of women and men are considered, valued and favoured equally.²

Equal opportunities for women and men indicate the absence of barriers to economic, political and social participation on the grounds of sex.⁴

Gender dimension in research content indicates the integration of the gender dimension in research content taking into account the biological characteristics and the evolving social/cultural features of both women and men. It invites researchers to conduct sex and gender analysis in the research process, when developing concepts and theories, formulating research questions, collecting and analysing data and using the analytical tools that are specific to each scientific area.³

Gender bias is the often unintentional and implicit differentiation between men and women by placing one gender in a hierarchical position relative to the other in a certain context, as a result of stereotypical images of masculinity and femininity. It influences both the participation of men and women in research (hence the underrepresentation of women) and the validity of research. An example of gender bias in research is research that focuses on the experience and point of view of either men or women, while presenting the results as universally valid.²

Gender balance refers to human resources and equal participation of women and men in all areas of work, projects or programmes.⁵

Intersectional factors such as racial or ethnic origin, age, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, or disability, combine with sex and gender to shape a person's or a group's experience and social opportunities, thereby influencing the form of discrimination and inequality they encounter.²

³ toolkit Gender in EU-funded research 2009 EC

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/gender/h2020-hi-guide-gender_en.pdf#page=10

⁵ <https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1148>

Empowerment of women is the process by which women gain power and control over their own lives and acquire the ability to make strategic choices.⁴

Gender analysis is the critical examination of how differences in gender roles, activities, needs, opportunities and rights/entitlements affect women, men, girls and boys in a given policy area, situation or context.⁴

Gender dimension are the ways in which the situation and needs of, and challenges facing, women and men (and girls and boys) differ, with a view to eliminating inequalities and avoiding their perpetuation, as well as to promoting gender equality within a particular policy, programme or procedure.⁴

3 The ENVISION Gender considerations

Gender considerations, in accordance to the Charter of Fundamental Rights in the EU and the European Research Area (ERA) priority 4, are to be implemented during the project based on the deliverable at hand **Gender Situation Analysis and Needs Assessment (GSANA)** outcomes thus ensuring:

- gender-sensitive project objectives, results and activities,
- gender-sensitive project partner assessment,
- gender-sensitive management arrangements,
- gender-sensitive indicators for monitoring, and
- gender-sensitive resource allocation.

The GSANA will allow the Consortium to understand how women and men are affected by different political, social, cultural, historical and legal factors in relation to the project and what their (different) needs might be. Meeting these specific needs in project interventions avoids discrimination of the sexes and allows a realistic assessment on its relation to gender rather than claiming beforehand that it is neutral. Additionally, the linkage between the environment and its different impact on both sexes are examined.

3.1 The Gender Equality Policy

A gender equality policy is a declarative statement which is a core organizational value. It sets guiding principles for mainstreaming gender equality objectives and accountability measures throughout organizational operations, structures, and programs. Establishing and implementing a gender equality policy means that an organization:

- benefits from the process of developing the policy, which requires identification and prioritization of gender gaps as well as broad internal consultation and awareness raising, and
- sets standards and guidelines, which allows an organization to harmonize and benchmark its gender equality in both operations and programming.⁶

The ENVISION Equality Policy is in accordance with the H2020 Programme Guidance on Gender Equality in Horizon 2020.⁷

⁶ http://www.sice.oas.org/genderandtrade/cida_gender-e_policies.pdf

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/gender/h2020-hi-guide-gender_en.pdf#page=10

ENVISION GENDER EQUALITY POLICY

The vision for Gender equality contributes substantially to improving the well-being of women and men. Over the 20th century important progress has been made but having entered the 21st century much remains to be done, towards achieving gender equality. ENVISION is committed to this vision and gender equality within research where inequality on any grounds, be it gender, race, sexual orientation, disability or ethnicity, is out of place. The tool to succeed in this vision is ENVISION Gender Equality Policy.

The Goal of the ENVISION Gender Equality Policy is to support the gender-sensitive dimension within the project team, results and activities.

This Policy is an integral part of the ENVISION project. Gender equality within the project is examined, in terms of:

1. Human resources: monitoring balance between women and men in the research teams and taking corrective actions when needed both within the consortium and external expert groups (i.e., Advisory Board, Lighthouse Customers).
2. Content: analysing and taking into account the possible differences between men and women, or males and females, in the research and innovation content (i.e., activities, deliverables, user requirements).

We take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the project. These aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level. Monitoring and evaluation of results and progress towards the promotion of gender balance will take place throughout the project.

The Gender Dimension is at all times integrated within ENVISION by:

- ✓ Determining the relevance of integrating sex and gender analysis in the project.
- ✓ Identifying gender differences that should be investigated and addressed.
- ✓ Examining gender assumptions that can influence scientific priorities, research questions, and methods.
- ✓ Evaluating whether research findings affect differently women and men.
- ✓ Maintain a gender balance in research teams and external experts' teams both in the core and decision-making teams.
- ✓ Recognising that every policy, program and project affects women and men differently.
- ✓ Encouraging partnerships between women and men.
- ✓ Designing specific measures to eliminate gender inequalities.

4 The Gender Equality Framework

4.1 Policies and Legal framework

Equality between women and men started being recognized in Treaties since the Treaty of Rome in 1957 and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU. Nonetheless, results of recent studies and reports show that a lack of significant progress and inequalities in many sectors between women and men remain.⁸

The Commission, since 1996, has adopted a 'dual approach' towards fulfilling the vision for a gender equality. The 'dual approach' involves mainstreaming a gender perspective in all policies, implementing at the same time specific measures to eliminate, prevent or remedy gender inequalities.

Gender equality in the European Union is protected by the following EU legal and policy documents.

- Articles 2 and 3(3) of the founding Treaty on European Union (TEU), Articles 21 and 23 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights, and Article 8 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) call for equality between women and men.
- The Treaty of Lisbon that includes a commitment to gender equality through Declaration No. 19, annexed to the Final Act of the Intergovernmental Conference that adopted the Treaty.
- The EU Economic Growth Policy (Europe 2020) that entails increasing women's labour market participation as an objective.
- The Barcelona targets that include a specific target on childcare coverage to facilitate the reconciliation of work and private life for both women and men.

Pay gaps and organisational diversity are also priorities for the European Commission directly linked with EU Funds' objectives. These priorities have been clearly set:

- in the legally binding Directive 2014/95/EU (on disclosure of non-financial and diversity information by certain large undertakings and groups),
- in the non-binding Recommendation 2014/124/EU (on strengthening the principle of equal pay between men and women through transparency) and
- in the EU action plan 2017-2019: 'Tackling the gender pay'.

The **framework for Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality 2016-2019** underlined that the EU Funds are the EU's main investment tool promoting gender equality through:

- continuous monitoring and support for Member States in achieving the Barcelona goals on childcare;
- taking into consideration public consultation results on work-life balance;
- by facilitating Diversity Charter platforms to support companies' increase the participation of women in labour-market;

⁸ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/608868/IPOL_STU\(2019\)608868_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/608868/IPOL_STU(2019)608868_EN.pdf)

- integrating a gender perspective into the European Agenda on Migration relative to barriers to migrant women’s employment;
- awareness-raising to promote women’s entrepreneurship.

The **2011 – 2020 Gender Equality Pact** consisted of the following measures relative to gender equality:

- to close gender gaps and combat gender segregation in the labour market,
- to promote better work-life balance for women and men, and
- to tackle all forms of violence against women.

The **European Pillar of Social Rights**, (2017), laid down the framework towards achieving better living and working conditions across the EU. It is laid down around three categories: equal opportunities and access to the labour market (including ‘key principle 2: gender equality’), fair working conditions, social protection, and inclusion.

The **Work-life Balance Directive** (EU 2019/1158) supports gender equality and concentrates on delivering key principles of the EU Pillar of Social Rights (key principle 9: work-life balance), via policy and legal measures.

The **2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development** was adopted in 2015 by all Members of the EU States and the United Nations. Gender equality is a cross-cutting aspect of all 17 global goals. Additionally, SDG 5: ‘Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls’ is dedicated to Gender. Paragraph 20 of the 2030 Agenda focuses on the need to close the gender gaps and support gender equality by gender mainstreaming. Moreover, a specific indicator of the SDG is dedicated on gender budgeting (indicator 5.C.1.).

4.2 Standards for mainstreaming Gender Equality

Traditional gender roles and disproportionate power relations drive discrimination against particular groups. Gender intersecting factors — e.g., age, class race, sexuality, disability, economic status, nationality, health status — may intensify exclusion, and prevent equal opportunities for all.

Gender equality mainstreaming is the process or means by which these unequal conditions are addressed to achieve the goal of gender equality. This requires the integration of gender in all organizational and institutional activities, an integration that should focus on the promotion of gender equality and women empowerment.

Over the years extensive policies, strategies, evidence reports, and guidelines across the gender and development sector and global organizations, networks etc. have been developed to achieve Gender Equality mainstreaming

The Minimum Standards for Mainstreaming Gender (as developed by The Gender Practitioners Collaborative) offer a common set of standards that has resulted from an extensive review of resources that can be applied by all types of organizations. They are outlined in the following and provide the framework for Gender Equality.⁹

⁹ The Gender Practitioners Collaborative, Minimum Standards for mainstreaming Gender Equality

1. Adopt a Gender Equality Policy

A gender equality policy sets the guiding principles for mainstreaming gender equality objectives and accountability measures throughout an organization, its operations, structures and programs.

2. Develop Organizational Culture and Capacity for Gender Equality

A commitment to promote gender equality requires that organizations have an enabling culture as well as staff and partners with the capacity to mainstream gender equality.

3. Conduct and Utilise Gender Analysis

A Gender analysis identifies gender specific and gender-differentiated needs and opportunities that may affect project outcomes and impacts on stakeholders. It is essential to incorporate monitoring and evaluation into gender analysis to assess progress and impact throughout a project.

4. Allocate Resources for Gender Equality

The promotion of gender equality requires allocation of resources. Resource allocations (e.g., budget, human resources) depend on the specific needs of a project.

5. Utilise Sex Disaggregated Data

The critical first step in understanding individuals' needs, roles, opportunities and vulnerabilities is the collection of sex- and age-disaggregated data. All data concerning individuals can be disaggregated by sex and are essential for monitoring gender inequalities.

6. Develop Gender Equality Indicators

In order to develop proper gender equality indicators, it needs to be ensured that the project has clearly identified gender equality goals. Indicators are to be selected in accordance with the findings of the gender analysis and the project's objectives.

7. Perform Risk Assessment and Develop mitigation strategies.

Risks can be similarly acute for both projects that are gender neutral and gender inclusive. Unintended consequences for project stakeholders could be for example criticism and exclusion. Team members and external experts may also be placed in dangerous or uncomfortable situations, or face personal, psychological, physical, or legal suffering. Factors that intensify risk may include sex, age, disability, ethnicity, religion, sexuality, and/or race. A thorough risk assessment is necessary to avoid potential reputational, legal, and financial impacts.

8. Monitor the status of Gender Equality.

Monitoring of the status of Gender performance determines the extent to which a project fulfills its commitment to mainstreaming gender equality. Monitoring also enables mitigation measures to be taken to correct imbalances or ensure compliance with policies and guidelines.

The above-mentioned guiding principles have been integrated within this deliverable and will be implemented throughout the ENVISION project.

5 ENVISION Gender Situation Analysis and Needs Assessment

This chapter presents the gender integration within the project following a Gender Situation Analysis and Needs Assessment.

All EU Member States have implemented national laws that provide protection against discrimination on the basis of sex. International human rights law also promote the obligation to promote gender equality and the empowerment of women. Apart from any legal obligation, it is generally accepted and has been empirically proven that that gender in research equality makes teams perform better and attracts top-level researchers. Accordingly, a gender-sensitive approach to the research content makes for higher quality and validity.¹⁰

Mainstreaming gender and intersecting factors in the design and delivery of R&I leads to:

- added value of research in terms of excellence, creativity and business opportunities,
- an in-depth understanding of all people's needs, behaviours and attitudes,
- goods and services better suited to the needs of all people and
- enhanced societal relevance of research and innovation.¹¹

The European Commission pursues a systematic and visible strategy to promote gender equality in science and research. Specifically, it recognizes that the relationship between women and research is threefold and therefore:

- women's participation in science and research must be encouraged,
- research must address women's needs as well as men's and
- there should be research on the gender question itself, to enhance understanding of gender issues in science and research.

These objectives are integrated in the Commission provisions for the implementation of Horizon 2020, at each stage of the research and innovation cycle as presented in the following figure.

¹⁰ GENDER IMPACT ASSESSMENT Gender Mainstreaming Toolkit, eige, 2016

¹¹ GENDERED INNOVATIONS, How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation European Commission, 2020

Figure 1: The Gender-Sensitive Research Cycle¹²

5.1 Gender Situation in the EU

- **Gender Equality**

The current state of Gender Equality in the EU is presented by the gender equality index. The Gender Equality Index is a composite indicator that measures the complex concept of gender equality based on the domains of Work, Money, Knowledge, Time, Power and Health. It is based on the EU policy framework and it assists in monitoring progress of gender equality across the EU over time.¹³

According to the data available in the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) portal (<https://eige.europa.eu/>), the equality status of the participating countries of the consortium is per the previously mentioned core domains:

¹² Toolkit Gender in European Commission Directorate-General for Research -funded research, EU, 2009

¹³ <https://eige.europa.eu/>

Table 1: Gender Equality Index per country¹⁴

Country	Index	Work	Money	Knowledge	Time	Power	Health
EU 28*	67.9	72.2	80.6	63.6	65.7	53.5	88.0
Belgium	71.4	74.7	88.7	71.4	65.3	55.7	86.5
Croatia	57.9	69.9	72.6	51.6	51.0	41.4	83.7
Cyprus	56.9	70.8	81.7	56.2	51.3	29.8	88.0
Greece	52.2	64.4	72.5	54.8	44.7	27.0	84.0
Lithuania	56.3	74.1	66.1	56.2	50.6	34.1	80.0
Serbia ^{15**}	55.8	68.2	60.2	57.3	48.7	37.3	84.0
Slovenia	67.7	73.1	83.0	55.9	72.9	55.0	86.9
UK	72.7	76.9	80.4	70.1	69.9	60.0	92.8

*The data for 2020 Index is mostly from 2018

**data for Serbia are from 2016

As it is presented in Table 1 six out of eight countries represented in the consortium score lower than the mean equality index of the EU. Overall performances are lower in the knowledge and time domain whilst higher in the domain of health.

- **The Gender Pay Gap**

The Gender Pay Gap is defined as the difference between the average hourly earnings of working men and working women. In 2018 women in the EU earned 14.1% less than men per hour or 86-euro cents for every €1 men earned. The Gender Pay Gap is not an indicator of the overall labour inequalities between women and men. In countries where the female employment rate is low, the pay gap tends to be lower than average. A high pay gap is usually characteristic of a labour market in which women are more concentrated in a restricted number of sectors and/or professions, or in which a significant proportion of women work part time. Even though the situation is improving, progress is very slow in the European Union with the gap only decreasing by just under 2 percentage points over the period 2010-2018.¹⁶ The pay gap situation in the Consortium partner countries is presented in the following map:

¹⁴ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2020/compare-countries/index/table>

¹⁵ Gender Equality Index for the Republic of Serbia Social Inclusion and Poverty Reduction Unit Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2016

¹⁶

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/aid_development_cooperation_fundamental_rights/2020_factsheet_on_the_gender_pay_gap.pdf

Figure 2: Map of the gender pay gap in EU-28

- **Gender in Research Content**

European research still shows a pronounced under-representation of women, particularly in the so-called hard sciences and in leadership positions. Gender equality in research is essential not only for fairness, but because it could help address current and future deficits in skilled labour within the EU.

This reality reflects an inefficient use of highly skilled women in the EU, which is a considerable loss of talent. The annual increase in women researchers is less than half the annual number of women PhD graduates. In addition to the low percentage of women researchers, women are also under-represented in top-level and decision-making positions in European research. The European Commission's "She figures"¹⁷ show that despite progress, gender inequalities in science persist. Women are also historically under-represented as the head of higher education institutions. However, recent data indicate that women have gained some ground.¹⁸

¹⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/she-figures-2018_en

¹⁸ Gender Mainstreaming Platform, Policy Areas, Gender in research, eige, 2016

According to EIGE’s Gender Statistics Database the share of female researchers is at 33.5% in the EU 28. Table 2 presents the share of female researchers in the countries of the consortium:

Table 2: Share of female researchers per partner country

Country	Share (%) of female researchers
EU 28	33.5%
Belgium	34.1%
Croatia	48.9%
Cyprus	37.9%
Greece	38.0%
Lithuania	50.7%
Serbia	49.2%
Slovenia	36.5%
UK	38.6%

Source: EIGE, 2015

Additionally, women to men ratio of authorships in all fields of R&D is equivalent to 1:2 in the EU 28. Details on the countries of focus are presented in Table 3:

Table 3: Share of female authorships per partner country

Country	Share (%) of female authorships
Belgium	0.5
Croatia	0.8
Cyprus	0.4
Greece	0.5
Lithuania	0.7
Serbia	1.0
Slovenia	0.6
United Kingdom	0.5
European Union - 28 countries	0.5

Source: EIGE, 2015

- **Gender Identity**

Regarding more explicit concepts of gender and that being gender identity, significant legislative changes have taken place over the last few years. Gender identity which is defined as a personal conception of oneself as male or female is intimately related to the concept of gender roles. The current state of gender identity / expression within the project’s focus can be summarized in Table 4:

Table 4: State of gender identity / expression per partner country

Country	Laws concerning gender identity/expression
Greece	✓ Under the Legal Gender Recognition Act 2017
Cyprus	✓ Forbids discrimination based on gender identity. ✗ Gender change is not legal.
Serbia	✓ Legal after 1 year of hormone therapy, surgery no longer required since 2019
Lithuania	✓ Gender change legal; surgery required
Croatia	✓ Act on the elimination of discrimination bans all discrimination based on both gender identity and gender expression. Gender change is regulated by special policy issued by Ministry of Health.
Belgium	✓ Since 2018, sex changes do not require sterilisation and surgery
Slovenia	✓ Gender change is legal
UK	✓ Under the Gender Recognition Act 2004
Greece	✓ Under the Legal Gender Recognition Act 2017

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LGBT_rights_in_Europe#cite_note-357

Equal treatment on the basis of sex in employment is covered by the Recast Directive. It presents probably the best known area of EU non-discrimination law. Trans, non-binary and intersex people may face gender discrimination comparable to cisgender men and women. However, on top of that they may experience problems related to their trans status or experience of intersex variance.¹⁹

- **The COVID-19 impact on Gender Equality**

COVID-19, like previous epidemics infect and affect men, women and other genders differently. Whilst indications suggest that mortality from COVID-19 is higher in men than women, the impact of the (short and longer term) socio-economic effects of COVID-19 fall disproportionately on women. Beyond this gendered effect, these outcomes intersect with other drivers of vulnerability i.e., ethnicity and sexual orientation. Importantly, these effects are not because of the pathogen itself, but as a consequence of the public health interventions and policies introduced by governments to minimise the spread of SARS CoV-2 pathogen.

These gendered affects are evident in several areas of interest. As women comprise of 76% of healthcare workers in EU but they also comprise much of the broader care sector. These jobs have increased exposure to infection with COVID-19. Women have also absorbed most of the informal and unpaid care in the COVID-19 pandemic too, as quarantine increased their time spend on childcare and domestic tasks. Some have significantly shifted their working patterns to be able to accommodate multiple paid and unpaid demands. Calls to domestic violence hotlines increased by 20 – 60 % across the EU, demonstrating a significant problem for societies and governments. Additionally, the pandemic has led to a distortion of health systems as health resources get diverted to manage the crisis at hand. This has several downstream effects for women, particularly in their access to safe sexual and reproductive health services (SRH). Women’s economic empowerment will likely continue to be

¹⁹ Trans and intersex equality rights in Europe – a comparative analysis, EC, Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2018

significantly affected in the coming months and years due to the sector wide effects of COVID-19 interventions. The highly feminised economy sectors which have been most significantly affected by lockdown measures are hospitality, recreation, tourism, and education/childcare. Finally, data which demonstrate the differential effect of COVID-19 and related policies are lacking. Fewer than 50% of countries globally are reporting sex-disaggregated data for COVID incidence and mortality and even fewer countries report disaggregated data to understand the distribution of the downstream socio-economic effects of COVID-19 interventions.²⁰

5.2 Gender Situation within the project

Gender aspects are relevant in this project in three ways, all of which will be addressed horizontally in the relevant WPs. More specifically:

- **Gender relevance to Work Packages**

This task (T2.5 Gender considerations) is specifically designed to clearly articulate the gender relevance to the project and its WPs. Gender is of relevance to all work packages of the project. Nonetheless some WPs that are directly related to user engagement and user needs are more closely related to gender aspects. Specific needs of both men and women must be addressed when examining user needs whilst gender specific considerations should be taken into account when designing a product and disseminating results. Taking gender into account and asking from the start who will use the results, when and how, can avoid an unintentional gender bias in the outcomes.

The WP that are linked to users, results and their dissemination as well as the deliverables that are considered significant for gender mainstreaming in the project are the following:

²⁰ The gendered impact of the COVID-19 crisis and post-crisis period Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs Directorate-General for Internal Policies PE 658.227- September 2020

Table 5: Work Packages and Deliverables Mainstreaming Gender

WP	Deliverable	Gender dimension
WP1 - Management		As follows per deliverable
D1.3	Initial Data Management Plan	Gender segregated data
D1.4	Intermediate Data Management Plan	Gender segregated data
D1.5	Intermediate report on Lighthouse Customers and Advisory Board feedback and actions taken	Equal representation
D1.6	Final Data Management Plan	Gender segregated data
D1.7	Final report on Lighthouse Customers and Advisory Board feedback and actions taken	Equal representation
D2.1	Review of current services provision	Equal representation of gender needs
WP2 - Commercial Service Requirements		As follows per deliverable
D2.2	Report of customer requirements from ENVISION services	Equal representation of gender needs
D2.3	Gender Situation Analysis and Needs Assessment	Present the gender dimension
D2.4	Guidelines on legal and ethical issues	Include gender issues and legislation
D2.5	Privacy Risk Assessment for ENVISION	Data on gender intersecting factors
D2.6	Draft Report of co-production of ENVISION services	Equal representation of gender needs
D2.7	Report of co-production of ENVISION services	Equal representation of gender needs
WP4 - ENVISION service		Incorporate gender considerations as defined in the co-production process
WP5 - Business cases implementation and evaluation		Business cases examining the gender dimension
WP6 - Commercialisation and exploitation		Target groups profiles considering gender issues
WP7 - Dissemination and Communication		As follows per deliverable
D7.2	Intermediate report on dissemination activities	Gender aspects of the target audience
D7.3	Draft report on dissemination activities	Disseminate results in a gender sensitive way
D7.4	Final report on dissemination activities	Present gender segregated data

- **Research implementation**

Given that the agricultural sector is male dominant and technologies can have a significant gender bias (considered as “toys for boys”) research findings need to overcome sex bias and apply to the specific needs of all sexes.

To this end data collection tools (such as questionnaires and interview checklists) need to be gender-sensitive, use gender-neutral language, and should make it possible to detect the different realities of men and women. This will help to avoid gender bias.

Gender and intersecting factors have so far been investigated (prior to this deliverable) regarding the Consortium gender synthesis as well within the workshops organized to investigate customer requirements. As the project proceeds and additional data are collected the tools used will also incorporate the previously mentioned principles. To add on that, data analysis will not routinely be disaggregated by sex, but it will work as a tool to lead to gender analyses. Systematically taking sex as a central variable, and analysing other variables with respect to it (e.g., sex and IT skills, sex and publications within the project) will provide significant and useful insights. Involving gender-balanced end-user groups in the course of the research is also a good way of guaranteeing the highest impact.

- **Gender relevance to Project Management**

To improve equality, it is important to acknowledge that bias and discrimination might indeed exist and to investigate what is going wrong. Reducing gender bias in research calls to support the active involvement of all participants in the process, benefit both men and women, at all levels. Actions may include: setting ratios for participation, putting in place monitoring systems, installing feedback mechanisms and appointing a trained gender equality officer.²¹

The ENVISION project has acknowledged the need for taking specific management measures from the proposal stage. To this end an Ethics Manager has been included in the project’s executive board and has been assigned duties from the beginning of the project.

The **Ethics Manager (EM), Ms. Maroulla Schiza (ETAM)**, will make sure that activities both within the consortium (i.e., equal participation, opportunities) as well as the project’s ecosystem such as the engagement of citizens and local actors, as well as the use of data, are conducted in an ethical manner, and take into account sex and gender considerations.

- **Gender balance within the Project Management Team**

Equal distribution between males and females in the Management Team has been considered from the proposal phase. The Project’s Coordinator is a woman, and the Consortium has assigned Managerial roles to women in the Executive Board in a significant percentage. More specifically the Executive Board is represented by women at a percentage of 71%. The figure below presents the organizational structure of the Project:

²¹ Toolkit gender in EU-funded research

Figure 2: Project Organizational Structure

- Gender balance within the Project Team**

Overall a gender balance within the Project Team is also maintained. The share of male -female participation in the project (Figure 3) is at 58%-42% whilst except for three of the Partners that present an all-male synthesis a balance in gender amongst project teams is achieved (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Share of male – female participation in Envision Project

Figure 4: Female Participation in Partner Teams

On the other hand, within the Project Team leading roles have been assigned in a less encouraging share of women. As depicted in the following figure women have leading roles in management teams – WPs and Task Leaders – at a lower percentage from 23%-36%. Nonetheless, considering that the team is coordinated by a female dominant team gender balance is considered to be established.

Figure 5: Female Participation in Leading Positions

- **Intersecting factors**

In order to assess gender intersecting factors, the consortium partners were asked to complete an anonymized questionnaire that contained questions on personal information regarding their type of employment, duration of life working years, level of education, marital status and number of children (esp. under the age of six) and their ethnicity. This assessment of the current situation of the members of the Consortium leads to specific conclusions according to their needs.

35% team members have work experience less than 10 years proving that the consortium offers the opportunity to less skilled personnel to grow, out of which 46% are women.

The overall duration of work life years is about 14.9 years whilst women in the consortium have a 14.7 mean of work life years, meaning they share equal experience and expertise to men.

The educational level amongst the Consortium team members the results (depicted in Table 6), presents a satisfactory performance amongst team members in the higher educational level (MSc – PhD). More specifically the share of male – female holding a higher degree of education is at 62%-38%, whilst women holding a Master’s Degree are four times more than men. Females also predominate in the below University level.

Table 6: Consortium Members’ Level of Education

Level of Education	Males	Females
Secondary Education	40%	60%
College Degree	0%	100%
University Degree	57%	43%
MSc	21%	79%
PhD	71%	29%

68% of the team members are married or are in a registered partnership whilst 55% of them have children. Additionally, 19% of team members have children younger than six. This observation expressed the need of the consortium to achieve a work – life balance whilst one out of five team members have increased responsibilities regarding childcare and need flexibility in their work. Finally, 20% of partners have a different ethnicity than the country they live in, whilst an equal distribution between the two sexes is observed.

No significant gender issues as thus observed, and a gender equality balance has already been succeeded in the ENVISION project team.

The needs that should be addressed to ensure the safeguarding of gender balance and equality include the following:

- Partner organisations will be responsible for ensuring and monitoring that their code of conduct is in accordance with their national and EU legislation on gender equality.
- Recruitment in the project should continue to ensure that both sexes have equal representation.
- The Consortium will offer equal opportunities to team members with increased childcare responsibilities i.e., by arranging project meetings and activities in a manner that everyone can attend (e.g., hybrid).
- National holidays, religious feasts days, summer holidays and school holidays should be considered when arranging project meetings and activities to ensure the participation of all team members regardless their ethnicity and taking into account their family needs.

- **Gender synthesis of the External Expert Groups**

Gender equality within the advisory board is also a main target of this project, as their views will provide an important insight in a targeted gender approach. The Advisory Board and the Lighthouse Customer Group have not yet been set up, but the goal of the Consortium is to build a team where gender balance is also achieved.

6 Stakeholder Gender Responsiveness

Over the last few decades digitalization has been seen to transform socioeconomic and political realities. The integration of digital technologies has changed the labour market, creating both opportunities and risks to gender equality. Although policy debates on the digital future of work have adopted gender-neutral perspectives, they do not address the central role of digitalisation in transforming gender relations. The EU digital strategy ‘Shaping Europe’s digital future’ presents a vision of digital transition that works for all, ‘putting people first and opening new opportunities for business’. The EU gender equality strategy 2020–2025 notes that integrating the gender perspective in this area is crucial in order to achieve the goal of gender equality. Even though significant policy changes are taking place, major challenges remain for gender equality in the digital world of work.²²

ENVISION aims to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land by making use of state of the art-technologies and fully digitalizing the provision of services tailored to fit PA’s and CB’s needs. Stakeholders of the agricultural sector though have particular gender responsiveness.

- **Gender and Agriculture**

Agriculture is one of the most dominant activities in the world economy and workforce and plays a significant role in food production, environmental protection, landscape preservation, rural employment and food security.

Women play a vital role in agricultural activities and they have a central role as agricultural producers, as well as agents to other agricultural activities. Nonetheless in comparison to men, they have lower access to productive assets (e.g., land) and services (e.g., financing). Various constraints impinge upon their equal participation in collective action as members of agricultural cooperative, and members of centralized and decentralized governance systems. In order for agricultural growth to reach its potential, gender disparities must be effectively addressed and reduced.²³

Despite increasing attention to gender issues, rural women still face serious disadvantages, compared to rural men, but also to urban women. Women farmers have significantly less access to, control over, and ownership of land and other productive assets compared to their male counterparts. Nevertheless, the number of farms run by women seems to be constantly growing. Data suggest that despite the vast differences among Member States, about 30% of farms across the EU are managed by women. Additionally, female farmers represent 30% of total EU farm managers. In addition, there is a great difference between women’s participation in full-time employment (less than 30%) in comparison to part-time jobs (around 52%). The most obvious particularity of part time-work is that it is a specific form of employment which primarily affects women. About 80% of all part-time jobs in the EU are occupied by women. The total and female employment in all agricultural sectors by working time is presented in the following figure.

²² Eige, Gender Equality Index 2020 — Digitalisation and the future of work

²³ <http://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/522504/>

Source: Eurostat

Figure 6: Total and female employment in agriculture, forestry and fishing by working time, EU-28, 2018

Finally, women tend to have smaller farms that are found to be on average 5.84 ha compared with 12.88 ha owned by male farm holders. Women take more calculated risks than men, yet it is still difficult for them to access loans. Women’s ideas for innovation are as marketable as men’s, but they are not recognised by predominantly male stakeholders²⁴

- **Gender and digital technologies**

The dispersion of technology is having a vast effect on the labour market and the types of skills needed in the economy and society. The creation of a digital single market that has been a key policy for the EU policy aims at supporting an inclusive digital society, by integrating ICT learning and skills acquisition across different sectors to provide women and men equal opportunities to develop.

Nonetheless, it has been found that gender mainstreaming is not satisfactorily developed in digital single market policies and that considerable differences remain between different EU Member States. The Women in Digital (WiD) Scoreboard is a mechanism, put in place by the Commission that assesses women’s inclusion in digital jobs, careers and entrepreneurship. According to WiD ‘stereotypes and preconceptions’ continue to create obstacles for women and girls, even in Member States where gender mainstreaming is advanced. This means that gender inequalities continue to prevent women from reaching their full potential and from taking advantage of women’s digital potential and current contributions.

Current policy debate focuses on the increased use of digital technologies and its impact on employment. The spread of new technologies is considered a way to effectively increase the

²⁴ The professional status of rural women in the EU, European Union, 2019

productivity and competitiveness of the European economy. As conceived in ENVISION a range of time-consuming or physically demanding routine tasks can be automated, enabling workers to focus on more creative tasks, increase added value of services provided and also lead to improvements in working conditions. However, technological progress has also the potential to be highly disruptive, as many jobs need to be reorganised and workers need to receive relative training.

Gender differences in the use of ICT at work persist in the EU. Over the past 5 years an increase of digital technologies has been noted in almost 9 out of 10 workplaces. Yet the gender gap remains, as women continue to use some digital technologies less frequently than men, a factor that may prove limiting to their employment prospects, and even more significantly in jobs that depend on the use of new technologies. Estimates predict that digitalisation can lead to a 10–20 % of jobs at risk.²⁵

- **Gender Distribution in the Core Stakeholder Groups**

The Core stakeholder Groups have been defined in the ENVISION Deliverable (D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan) and involve Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies. Statistics on their gender synthesis are not available and to this end estimates on such data were provided by project partners. These data indicate a significantly high participation of women within their workforce and specifically:

Table 7: Estimate on Gender Distribution within representative consortium Pas /CBs

Paying Agency / Certification Body	Women	Men
NPA – Lithuania NATIONAL PAYING AGENCY	74%	26 %
LEAF -UK LINKING ENVIRONMENT AND FARMING LBG	85%	15%

To this end user requirements of ENVISION services need to incorporate gender aspects, as has already been the approach of the research team in the relative task (WP2 – Task 2.2 Identification of PAs' and CBs' needs).

²⁵ Gender Equality Index 2020 Digitalisation and the future of work: a thematic focus European Institute for Gender Equality

7 Gender Specific Project Dissemination

The Communication Strategy is designed to help the project partners communicate effectively to achieve the project's core objectives. It provides a useful roadmap for identifying who needs to be reached and what and when they need to hear to ensure the project is a success. (D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan).

Through this deliverable gender aspects in the dissemination issues of the project and its results will also be tackled in the, focusing on the appropriate channels that need to be used in order to ensure equal reach to all sexes.

Following the Toolkit Gender in EU-funded research recommendations four relevant gender aspects have come up in the context of the project's dissemination strategy.

1. Gender distribution within the team responsible for dissemination

This aspect is relevant to the point that a range of gender differences and inequalities persist in research and innovation and thus the team responsible for the dissemination of the project's results has been formed in a way that equal representation of gender within may ensure an equal dissemination perspective. In Table 8 the gender distribution of communication managers per partner is presented:

Table 8: Communication managers at individual partners per gender

Partner	Gender
DRXS	Female
NOA	Female
NPA	Female
LV	Male
CAPO	Male
OCS	Female
EV ILVO	Male
LEAF	A: Female B: Male
URDG	Male
ITC	A: Female B: Male
ETAM SA	Female
INOS	Male
AgroApps	Female
Total No of managers	15
%males	47%
%females	53%

As it is apparent from Table 8 a gender balance is established within the communication team and an equal distribution of male -female managers has been achieved (47% -53%).

2. Representation of gender in the disseminated materials (including gender-sensitivity and inclusiveness).

The design of dissemination materials needs to take under consideration the risk of gender stereotyping especially given the traditionally male dominant sectors the project is tackling. Gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of dissemination tools and platforms can be guided by the following. The language used needs to pay particular attention to be gender inclusive at all times (i.e., one instead of he, or people instead of men). Language accessibility is another issue and technical language, and terminology should be avoided when news is presented to the general public. As with language, images may also be biased. The imagery used in dissemination material should not challenge or reinforce stereotypes. Therefore, images of women in active roles should be equally used in the roles of the project’s target groups (i.e., researchers, IT specialists). Finally, Social Media Gender differences need to be taken into account.²⁶

Generally, females use social networking sites to make connections and stay in touch with family or friends. Men, on the other hand are found to use social media to perform research, gather relevant contacts and ultimately increase their status. They also have different preferences in social media platforms (See Table 9). These differences need to be examined to achieve equal reach of dissemination to both genders.

Table 9: Social Media Platform by Gender Use²⁷

Platform	Female Users (%)	Male Users (%)
Snapchat	70	30
Pinterest	60	40
Instagram	58	42
Facebook	52	48
Twitter	47	53
LinkedIn	46	54
YouTube	45	55

In order to ensure that equal reach of female and male users Facebook – Twitter – LinkedIn and YouTube are already used for the project communication -dissemination activities that ensure a 50-50 reach to genders. The website has been designed in a gender-neutral way using images that present technology and not people, whilst the language used is also neutral. The promotion of the female role in research will be addressed according to gender equality guidelines.²⁸

3. Gender aspects of the target audience

Target audiences should also be also examined in their expected gender reach. The Direct Target groups examined present as previously mentioned a strong female representation in their workforce,

²⁶ https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Niall-Dunphy/publication/336414212_Gender_Inclusivity_Dissemination_Guidelines/links/5da0722f299bf116fe9cf455/Gender-Inclusivity-Dissemination-Guidelines.pdf

²⁷ <https://www.brandwatch.com/blog/men-vs-women-active-social-media/>

²⁸ <https://www.openuphub.eu/component/k2/item/633-checklist-for-gender-in-dissemination>

although further investigation is needed. More focus should be given in the remaining target groups as the ICT industry and Agricultural sector that as previously described present an unbalanced gender distribution. To this end focused dissemination actions on channels that will enable the engagement of women should take place to ensure equal reach to sexes (i.e., women associations, corporations etc.). Specific events or publications in gender focused organisations, networks or gatherings could add on to the project's impact on both sexes (i.e., <https://www.womeninresearch.org/>, <https://wfan.org/>, <https://www.forwomeninscience.com/>).

Target groups have so far been identified as general groups (i.e., farmers, not male-female farmers) and not based on gender representation. Dissemination actions will maintain focus on gender.

4. Gender sensitive data reporting

Over the course of the project sex segregated data will be collected and analysed. Collecting and analysing gender-specific data is not enough if they are omitted from the published results. Gender should be included in 'mainstream' publications as it is as much part of daily reality as any other variable studied. The dissemination strategy should additionally focus on presenting gender related findings of the project to relevant gender differences that came up in the course of the project. Relative examples include presentation of gender statistics, tables, figures and descriptions that focus on the gender balance within the project.

The project dissemination and communication plan were set on M3 and specific guidelines / indicators on the gender topic were not integrated at the time. Nonetheless as previously mentioned following the project's gender mainstreaming philosophy and gender balance/ opportunities in assigning key roles in dissemination managers per partner has been achieved thus ensuring that a gender perspective will be followed within dissemination actions. Additional issues that need to be considered in the dissemination and communication plan in the course of the project will be tackled in the following deliverables (intermediate – draft – final report).

8 Gender-Sensitive Monitoring Plan

Every project should be assessed, using its established gender indicators, to determine whether or not its gender objectives are being met. Monitoring should take place at regular intervals and a contingency plan identifying probable risks and mitigation measures needs to be in place to provide the corrective actions in case the objectives are not being met.

Gender-sensitive monitoring and evaluation unveils the degree to which a project succeeds in addressing the needs of women and men. It additionally assesses the impact it has on gender relations and defines the gender aspects that should be integrated into monitoring and evaluation systems. Monitoring gender issues can effectively project progress made on gender equality issues. Gender-responsive monitoring and evaluation can take place by using both qualitative and quantitative data, providing useful data on the project's performance on gender equality.²⁹ As described in previous chapters the objectives on gender equality and mainstreaming relative to this project are:

- Equal representation (amongst the Project Team, Lighthouse Customers and Advisory Board).
- Include gender issues in relevant deliverables.
- Present sex segregated data.
- Integrate gender aspects in dissemination issues.

In Chapter 5 the current status of performance of these objectives has been presented. In order for their effective monitoring a set of indicators needs to be developed that will enable their qualitative and quantitative monitoring. More specifically:

1 Equal representation

At this point equal representation has been calculated for the project team as:

- Coordination team: Share of women in coordination team.
- WP Leaders & Task Leaders: Share of women in Leading Roles.
- Dissemination team: Share of female Communication Managers.
- Project Team: Share of female participation in the project.

The indicators for which values are not yet available are Share of women in Advisory Board and Share of women in LHC Groups.

The monitoring plan for the above objective can be monitored quantitatively as shown in Table 10:

²⁹

<https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1217#:~:text=Gender%2Dsensitive%20monitoring%20and%20evaluation%20is%20used%20to%20reveal%20whether,into%20monitoring%20and%20evaluation%20systems.>

Table 10: Gender Equality Monitoring Plan

Indicator	Target value	Current value	Risk	Mitigation measures	Monitoring period	Person responsible
Share of women in Executive Board	~50%	71%	Failing to succeed equal participation of men and women	Assign duties in following tasks	Yearly	Ethics manager Coordinator
Share of women in Leading Positions (WP – Task Leaders)	~50%	23%	Failing to succeed equal participation of men and women	Assign duties in following tasks	Every six months	Ethics manager Coordinator
Share of women in the consortium	~50%	42%	Failing to succeed equal participation of men and women	Recruit female members in all male schemes	Every six months	Ethics manager Coordinator
Share of women in Advisory Board	~50%	0%	Failing to succeed equal participation of men and women	Invite more female members	Every three months until establishment	Task Leader Ethics Manager Coordinator
Share of women in LHC	~50%	N/A	Failing to succeed equal participation of men and women	Invite more female members	Every three months until establishment	Task Leader Ethics Manager Coordinator

Necessary resources for the achievement of these objectives are:

- Establishment of a Gender Equality Culture within the team

This will be achieved by dedicated presentations by the Ethics Manager both to the Consortium and the Coordination team that will promote the project's Gender Policy as well as reporting on the gender situation analysis as it progresses. Estimated time needed for this task is about three Person Months.

- Include gender issues in relevant deliverables

The deliverables that explicitly tackle gender issues are identified and presented in Table 5. The objective in this case can be assessed qualitative. The deliverables that should present gender issues will be assessed by internal reviewers as to the extent they have included the gender dimension.

Corrective actions will be taking place in the form of reviewers comment before the final submission of deliverables.

- Present sex segregated data

Sex segregated data will be presented within the deliverables identified in Table 5 and mainly in the deliverable at hand. The objective may also be assessed qualitatively within the deliverables.

2 Integrate gender aspects in dissemination issues

This objective will be assessed both qualitatively and quantitatively. Methods of dissemination ensuring gender mainstreaming and gender friendly language and other intersecting issues will be assessed by internal reviewers in the frames of upcoming deliverables. The indicators that can be measured and thus quantitatively assessed are presented in the following table:

Table 11: Equal Gender Dissemination Monitoring Plan

Indicator	Target value	Current value	Risk	Mitigation measures	Monitoring period	Person responsible
No of publication or presence in events with a gender focus	<1	0	Fail to succeed in equal dissemination	Enhance dissemination efforts	Annually	Dissemination manager Ethics Manager Coordinator
Engagement of women associations	<3	0	Fail to succeed in equal dissemination	Involve project partners (PAs & CBs) to enhance dissemination efforts	Annually	Dissemination manager Ethics Manager Coordinator

The Commission monitors the implementation of gender as a cross-cutting issue, according to the following indicators which are used on an annual basis to determine the prevalence of gender as a cross-cutting issue³⁰:

- % of women participants in Horizon 2020 projects
- % of women project coordinators in Horizon 2020
- % of women in advisory groups, expert groups, evaluation groups and panels
- % of projects with gender dimension in the project design.

These indicators are in accordance with the project objectives and are being monitored through the presented monitoring plans. They are to be reported for each periodic review.

Reporting will be presented in Consortium and Progress meetings

³⁰ H2020 Programme Guidance on Gender Equality in Horizon 2020

9 Conclusions

The strong presence of women in the ENVISION project is expected to contribute to gender awareness in research and the project's thematic area. As far as month six (6) of the project a gender balance has been established within the Consortium, whilst an equal gender distribution is targeted in the External Expert & Advisory Group.

The gender needs that have been identified mainly focus on gender mainstreaming within all WP, ensuring the balance of work – family life of team members and a balanced dissemination of project results between genders. A monitoring plan of gender equality has been set, with gender specific indicator and mitigation measures in case identified risks emerge.

The Gender Equality Policy is expected to create the gender sensitive culture within the team and will be ENVISION's tool to support the gender-sensitive dimension within the project results and activities.

End of Document

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